

Research Article

MYSTERIOUS EmoGate

Savina A/P A.Saiman¹, Aina Fauziaa Ahmad Shafian², Nor Husna Mohd Tambyzy³, Nursabirah Ainaa Burhanuddin⁴

¹ Pusat Tingkatan 6, SMK Seri Budiman Gerik Perak; 0000-0002-5160-6964

² Pusat Tingkatan 6, SMK Seri Budiman Gerik Perak

³ Pusat Tingkatan 6, SMK Seri Budiman Gerik Perak

⁴ Pusat Tingkatan 6, SMK Seri Budiman Gerik Perak

* Correspondence: vinavin23@gmail.com; 60195155849

In today's day and age, students face problems in structuring sentences appropriately, using low frequency words in their essays due to various factors. They have negative perceptions towards learning new vocabulary, and to make it worse, they feel afraid to explore new words. In this endeavor, they are only proficient at B1 and B2 levels, and they do not know how to distinguish words with similar spellings or pronunciations while reading or speaking. Thus, this game is aligned to meet the purpose and aim of making students learn low-frequency words effectively and much more easily. Needless to say, by playing this game, students can memorize low-frequency words, including their meanings and CEFR levels, as they gradually play the game. The impact of this innovation is that students were able to obtain C1 and C2 levels for reading. Apart from that, we have spread the use of our Mysterious EmoGate game to other students at our school and other schools, parents, and so on through links, QR codes, YouTube, and Telegram.

Keywords: Low-Frequency Words, Vocabulary, Reading, Games, Memorize

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10463952

Copyright: © 2024 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

Students do not know how to differentiate low-frequency words (A word is not commonly used) with similar meanings, spellings, or pronunciations while reading via Papermode Quizizz. They have negative perceptions towards learning new vocabulary. In addition, 25 % of students achieved B1 and B2 levels in Papermode Qizizz, which placed them in the low bands (R). W. P. (2023).

However, Mysterious EmoGate is an innovation designed to help students improve their English language skills for their studies and everyday life. This game encourages critical thinking, a sense of adventure, and an openness to customization that will help students in the classroom (Mogea, T.). (2022). This innovation is a composite game that includes a QR code to integrate technology into this innovation (K. H. (2021). Integration of digital learning and hands-on games can create an enjoyable learning atmosphere, ensuring that students are active and receive meaningful information (Niitemaa, M.). L. (2020).

Mysterious EmoGate," students can stick or scan the cups with emojis to play. There are many low-frequency words which they have never heard before and can learn. By doing so, students can define or at least identify in terms of a problem domain, which is the lack of use of low-frequency words among students (Clark, R. (2023)). The question is, how would they know the level of their vocabulary

achievement? Well, here is how they can do it. In the "Mysterious EmoGate", we provide them with games and quizzes to test their level according to the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR), which are C1 and C2. This learning experience can gain few aspects in students' critical thinking skills. For instance, observation, analysis, inference, communication, and problem-solving. In summary, the playfulness element that we bring to our game is a fundamental factor in student satisfaction and engagement in learning (Erickson, P. (2019)). Thus, utilizing a new digital way by scanning the QR codes for questions and answering in a Lino memo pad plus with manual interactive games can help enhance students' engagement in learning.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 The Meaning of MYSTERIOUS EmoGate

Mysterious means difficult or impossible, while emo stands for emojis, means depictions of human emotions, living beings, objects, and even certain symbols, and gate means we use the gates as barriers to make this game more challenging and fun.

2.2 Innovation Prototype

For this innovation, we used small and big cups, ice cream sticks, emoji stickers, a box, mounting board, strap, sponge, and balloon to make this innovation a finished product. QR codes are provided to ease the students' access to the application. Users just need to click the link above or scan the QR code to go to our quizzes that contain questions of low-frequency words. Users need to scan the QR code to start answering the questions.

To set up the Mysterious EmoGate game, we have to choose two players to play this game. For this innovation, we have a box that contains a game base and the materials that need to be assembled by the players. There are colorful tokens that have been pasted with the emojis' stickers. Players have to place the box on the table. On top of the box, there are rules and regulations on how to play this game. Players have to arrange the cups first and then stand the gates into the sponges. To determine who starts the game first, players have to roll the tokens. Not to forget, I am proud to say that we have three sets of the Mysterious EmoGate game, which makes this game more interesting and fun (Turgunova, F.). (2022)). Thus, this is the final product of our innovation once it has been assembled. We have two different colors of containers to separate the 2 players. The game can now begin. Firstly, each player must take a ball from the box and place it in the cup which is labelled "start". Next, the player must pull the balloon so that the ball rolls on its way. The ball will move randomly into one of the cups' emojis. Once the ball lands in any of the cups, the player must scan the QR code that has been pasted on the cup. The QR code will direct the player to a question. Player has to answer the question on the memo pad on the right side of the smartphone and then post the correct answer. After the first question is answered, the player has to pull of the cup to prevent the other player from getting the same question. There are two cups that contain bombs where the players will not receive a token. The tokens function to determine who has the most tokens at the end of the game. The winner will be announced based on the most tokens collected with the allocated marks.

3. FINDINGS

The data in the pre-quizizz shows the students' marks after they answered individually. Only 25% of the students answered thirteen questions correctly. This proves that they did not practice using low frequency words and using appropriate English in their daily life, making it difficult for them to answer the questions correctly. The data in the post-quizizz was collected after the students used our innovation. It shows that 67% of the students showed a lot of improvement from the score of their second quiz. It is safe to say that this application had a positive impact on them, knowing better words for each question. (S. Banu,2023).

Picture 1 : Pre - Quizizz

Picture 2 : Post - Quizizz

Additionally, these were the reflections from the students “I am actually lazy to memorize the low-frequency words, but by playing MYSTERIOUS EmoGame, “I feel fun and managing to improve my vocabularies”, “This game’s concept saves me time” and “I have the confidence that I can score with flying colors in MUET by memorizing many words.”

4. DISCUSSION

This application is the latest innovation that has never been created before. This innovation is also very different compared to other innovations as we have included more elements in one game. We use the medium of YouTube as a transmitter of knowledge to students. We have spread the use of our Mysterious EmoGate game to students,parents at our school, and other schools, parents and so on through links, QR codes, YouTube, and Telegram. They enjoyed playing our innovation and were able to apply the tips we provided in the same video. The teacher also gave her feedback on how our innovation helped her teach her students English.

4.1 Commercialization

Our application is built to help students learn vocabulary better. This application is flexible as you can use it online despite having a short time due to your daily schedule or your availability during your leisure time. For online use, we have provided a QR code for students to play. The cost of materials is affordable, and it is a finished product. Estimated buyers are 100 people.

4.2 Novelty & Uniqueness

Our innovation is colorful and catchy (cups with emojis/balloons), thus it can attract students to play this game. It is also completed with CEFR Level (3 sets), so undoubtedly it is an interactive game. Our innovation is creative and stimulates critical thinking. On the other hand, it can be used by other skills/other subjects (science & arts). We can say that our innovation is a manual game + a digital way.

4.3 Originality

For this innovation, we did not identify any similar topics aligned with our project. This proves that it is fully our own idea, which we made ourselves (independently), and it is our own original idea.

5. CONCLUSION

Overall, one of the impacts of our innovation is that students have managed to obtain C1 and C2 levels for reading and can attain their objectives by using appropriate words. The innovation that we built is very useful in helping students learn more low-frequency words. Students and teachers also had fun while playing the game, as it is user-friendly and saves time and energy. It can also improve students' speaking skills indirectly. In order to score a high band in MUET speaking, language is vital, and this innovation is an interesting and enjoyable approach that can be applied in the classroom. Lastly, it is helpful for the future.

REFERENCES

- Clark, R. (2023). *Meaningful games: Exploring language with game theory*. MIT Press.
- Erickson, P. (2019). *The world the game theorists made*. University of Chicago Press.
- VR Manipatruni, NS Kumar, MR Karim, and S Banu (2023). *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*, 17 (13).
- Turgunova, F. (2022). USE OF INTERACTIVE GAMES IN TEACHING LANGUAGE AS A SECOND LANGUAGE. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 1(19), 349-351.
- Chee, K. M., & Tan, K. H. (2021). QR Codes as a Potential Tool in Teaching and Learning Pronunciation: A Critical Review. *Higher Education and Oriental Studies*, 1(1).
- Niitemaa, M. L. (2020). Informal acquisition of L2 English vocabulary: Exploring the relationship between online out-of-school exposure and words at different frequency levels. *Nordic Journal of Digital Literacy*, 15(2), 86-105.
- Putra, R. W. P. (2023). Improving Students' Vocabulary Through Paper-Mode Quizizz: A Classroom Action Research in Indonesian EFL Setting." *English Learning Innovation (englie)*, 4(1), 22-31.
- Mogea, T. (2022). STUDENTS' CRITICAL THINKING ABILITY IN ENGLISH TEACHING AND LEARNING. *Jurnal Pendidikan dan Sastra Inggris*, 2(3), 157-171.